

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

Evaluation Report

(acceptance note) for

TEBT-2024-0009

Submission Information Table

Submission Title	A comprehensive item bank of internal validity issues of relevance to in vitro toxicology studies
Submission Reference	TEBT-2024-0009
Handling Editor	Olwenn Martin, ORCID: 0000-0003-2724-7882
Number of Reviewers	2
Submission Type	Stage Two Manuscript
Preprint DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11077132
Evaluation Type	Acceptance Note :: Round 1
Evaluation Date	11 October 2024
Recommendation	Accept
Handling Editor's Explanation for Recommendation	Authors received exhaustive detailed comments during the first round of peer review. They comprehensively revised the manuscript, entirely restructuring and simplifying it. The authors have addressed all comments and substantially improved the readability and usefulness of the manuscript.

Summary of the article

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

This manuscript reports the results of the first step of the development of a risk-of-bias tool (INVITES-IN) for in vitro (cell cultures) studies, the protocol for which has been previously published [here](#). This involved the creation of an “item bank”, a database of study assessment concepts that may be relevant to evaluating the internal validity of in vitro toxicology studies. These were derived from seven literature sources and the transcribed discussions of three focus groups. Assessment criteria plausibly relating to internal validity were disaggregated, normalised and then mapped onto a set of bias domains. The resulting item bank contains 405 items that may be important for evaluating the internal validity of in vitro toxicology studies.

Editorial triage deemed that the manuscript details both any deviations from planned methods and the results of this exercise in a very transparent and complete manner. Data for different stages of analysis are supplied as supplemental material. There were a few minor omissions that were addressed after peer review.

The assessment of the two reviewers after the first round of peer review differed widely between that of the reviewer who had previously reviewed the protocol for this study and the reviewer who had not. This suggested that information critical for the reader to understand the rationale for and significance of the work presented in the published protocol was not sufficiently relayed in the manuscript. The authors were advised to provide clarifications about the rationale, objectives, and methods for the overall project and this specific step, as well as justification and indication of the utility of the item bank for the wider scientific community.

In response to reviewers’ comments, the authors comprehensively revised the manuscript. The whole manuscript was restructured and simplified. Notable changes include a revised introduction better describing the overall rationale for performing the study in the first place, definitions of all main terms, an overview of the overall process of the development of the INVITES-IN tool, the objective of the item bank step and how its results fit in the development of the tool. Further, the rationale for the selection of the item bank method and the scope of the item bank have been clarified. Finally, a detailed description of the structure and guidance on how to use the item bank have been added.

Acceptance note

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor after 1 round of revision in response to 1 round of editorial triage and 1 rounds of peer-review.

During triage, the handling editor identified three minor issues with the initial submission that could be addressed after peer-review. These were resolved by reviewing declaration of interests, citing the software used to generate a figure and renaming the supplementary files with plain English names.

During peer-review, the evaluators recommended that authors provide clarifications about the rationale, objectives, and methods for the overall project and this specific step, as well as justification and indication of the utility of the item bank for the wider scientific community. The authors addressed these issues by restructuring and simplifying the manuscript. Specifically, the introduction was revised to better describe the rationale of the study, define main terms, clarify the objective, scope and rationale for the item bank step. Additionally, a guidance document to accompany the item bank has been produced.

The following points of scientific interest were surfaced by the review process; the subjectivity or other limitations such time and resources of some methodological processes should be clearly identified and recognised in the manuscript, transparency is more important than perfect methods.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at [10.5281/zenodo.12801963](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12801963).